

A new blister mite pest of rice in the Philippines

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Aceria saccharini (Acari: Eriophyidae), a blister mite pest of rice, has been reported on sugarcane in Indonesia, Australia, Taiwan, China, and India. It damages leaf sheaths and transmits streak virus disease. In 1988, it was reported to have transferred to rice in Sulawesi, Indonesia (IRRN 16 (1) 22). Now it has been found in Central and Southern Luzon, Philippines.

Injury to rice is similar to that caused by thrips, and damage symptoms can be confused with tungro. Feeding produces white, chlorotic, shallow, gall-like pustules. Blisters vary in length (0.20-18 mm) and width (0.01-10 mm). The long proboscis of the mite probes vertically into the upper or lower epidermis of the leaf, lacerating tissues and torturing both epidermal and parenchymous tissue cells. Mites from different localities differ in color, from cream to pale yellow or orange pink. The orange pink form is more prevalent. The adult mite is microscopic in size (0.16 ± 0.04 mm long, 0.05 ± 0.002 mm wide) (see photo). Mites moving on the leaf surface can be seen with the naked eye. With magnification, the adults appear wormlike with a shield-shaped head. The body bears two pairs of slender legs anteriorly. All legs have claws, with 6-7 protruding feathered ray hairs each. The abdomen is annulated with 78-82 rings and three pairs of ventral setae. Eggs are spherical 0.05 mm diameter, pale yellow turning to orange pink when about to hatch. The pale yellow larva has a droplet-like shape with a large globular anterior, tapered posterior, and a pair of moderately long anterior legs. The proto-nymph, twice the size of a larva, is whitish to light yellow with a thin layer of golden yellow hairs laterally. Both are orange pink when mature.

We monitored mite densities in 14 fields during the wet season. Three leaves each were sampled from the bottom, middle, and top plant areas a seedling, maximum tillering, panicle initiation, and ripening stages. Ten samples per growth stage were bagged separately or placed in vials with 80% alcohol. The mite population reached its peak (mean of $2,485 \pm 306$ / three leaves) during the late Nov-Dec post-monsoon period. *A. saccharini* preferred relatively young, greenish foliage, with this order of frequency: maximum tillering > panicle initiation > seedling > ripening stage. It was most abundant in the middle to apical one-third stratum of the dorsal leaf surface.

A. saccharini elongated adult, spherical transparent egg and larva magnified on the underside of a rice leaf

International Rice Research Newsletter 1991. Volume 16 No. 4 pages 21-22.